

death and decay of old roots. Root dry weight increased from 14 DH to 28 DH, and then declined gradually up to 75 DH. New roots developed 14-28 DH, but they grew very slowly. Plants exhibited roots from the ratoon tillers at 21 DH. Rooting was more profuse and rapid from lower ratoon tillers than from upper tillers. The mean dry weight of roots from ratoon tillers was 11-19% of the total dry weight at 42 DH, ratoon flowering, and harvesting.

Total root dry weight decreased after 28 DH perhaps because main crop roots were decaying as evidenced by 75 to 85% dead roots at ratoon harvest.

Ratoon tiller development in IR44 appears to depend on the main crop root system for nutrients at least up to 21 DH. Thereafter, the requirements were partially supplemented by new roots from ratoon tillers. However, the contribution of new roots seems very low. It is suggested that care be taken to avoid damaging main crop roots at harvest. □

Root production in the ratoon crop of IR44, IRRI.

Effects of N application on rice yield under drought

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We studied the interaction of N and K on rice yield in a field experiment at TNRRI, Sep 1982-Jan 1983 season. Zero, 50, 100, or 150 kg N/ha and 0, 41.5, or 83 kg K/ha with 22 kg P/ha were applied in 3 replications to IR20.

Soil was an Adanur series, very deep, noncalcareous grey brown, clay loam, with sand layers below 110 cm. Soil had pH 6.7, 2.23% organic matter, 0.11% total N, 36.0 meq CEC/100 g, 67.0 kg available P/ha, 0.45 meq exchangeable K/100 g, and 38.9% water-holding capacity.

There was an unusual drought in the Cauvery Delta during the study. We studied the effect of fertilization on rice grown under drought conditions. The crop was irrigated for only 2 wk after transplanting. Drought developed gradually. Surface irrigation was provided

Grain yield of rice under different N fertilization and drought conditions.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	2.6
50	2.1
100	2.1
150	1.9
CD	0.4

at wide intervals. Water stress was acute from heading to harvest.

Grain yield (mean of three replications) is shown in the table. Under drought conditions, N application considerably decreased yield. There also was a marginal yield decrease with increasing N application. K application did not affect rice yield. □

Evaluation of soil zinc fertility parameters for rice

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We evaluated equilibrium soil-solution Zn concentration in $\mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml}$ (intensity, C), Zn remaining adsorbed on soil in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ (capacity, q), Zn supply parameters (unitless unified terms of intensity, capacity, and buffering capacity factors, SP), and corrected supply parameters (unitless new parameter, CSP) at 15° and 30°C and their averages as soil Zn fertility index in a pot experiment.

Twenty Mollisols were equilibrated in duplicate for 2 h with 0.01M CaCl₂ solution (soil solution ratio 1:10) at 15° and 30°C, and C was determined. Using C, q at 15° and 30°C were calculated: $q_{30^\circ\text{C}} = (K_1 \cdot C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C}) / (K_2 + C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C})$ and $q_{15^\circ\text{C}} = (q_{30^\circ\text{C}} + C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C}) - (C \text{ at } 15^\circ\text{C})$, where K₁ was adsorption maxima ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$) and K₂ was constant relative to adsorption energy ($\mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml}$). The K₁ = (intercept)⁻¹ and K₂ = (K₁, slope) were estimated for each soil at 15° and 30°C in a separate Zn adsorption study in the range of 5 to 30 μg added Zn/g soil from the equation (Zn adsorbed by soil, $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$) = $(1/K_1) + (K_2/K_1) \cdot (\text{Zn in solution, } \mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml})^{-1}$. Expected interaction term of intensity, capacity, buffering capacity ($b = (K_2/K_1) \cdot (q_2/C_2)$,